

THE ROLE OF PUBLIC AUTHORITIES IN THE TRANSITION TO A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

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Abstract

Purpose – To investigate the current state of circular economy and green public procurement implementation among public authorities.

Methodology/approach - We conducted descriptive and a regression analyse on a sample of 122 participants.

Findings – One of the most frequently perceived barrier to the implementation of the circular economy is the lack of people with expertise in the field, the lack of knowledge on circular economy and green public procurements.

Research limitations/implications – One limitation is that the sample size is insufficient to extrapolate to develop general assumptions on a larger scale.

Practical implications – These findings can further contribute to the elaboration of a conceptual framework for embedding circular economy within the public authorities.

Originality/value – Studying the importance of the public sector in the transition to a circular economy, highlighting the behaviors, barriers and facilitators in this transition.

Key words: Circular Economy, Green Public Procurement, Circular Cities

Introduction

Concerns about the scarcity of the earth's natural resources are growing rapidly in an ever-growing global economy, in the context of a world where resources are limited. Furthermore, resource extraction and use are both associated with pollutant emissions and waste generation, exacerbating the negative environmental impacts (Hashimoto, Fischer-Kowalski, Suh, and Bai, 2012). Today, there is no doubt that humanity is a major contributor to the environmental changes and instability that the Earth is experiencing (Rockström et al., 2009; Steffen, Crutzen, and McNeill, 2007). Much of these issues can be traced back to the long-standing linear economic regime, which has been characterized by the "take-make-dispose" paradigm, which has been identified as inherently unsustainable in the long term in the context of a resource-constrained world (Lieder and Rashid, 2016; Rice, 2007, Rada et al., 2017).

The circular economy (CE) paradigm is gaining popularity as a means of addressing current sustainability challenges and easing the transition away from the linear model of production and consumption. The public sector is essential because it is a significant buyer, consumer, and user of goods and services, but it is also an important decision-making factor and a model of good practises for others. Although, public sector and circular economy together has received very little attention in CE research (Klein et al., 2020).

The role of public authorities and how they can become key elements in this process is an important factor in facilitating the transition to a circular economy, and it is examined in this study. The public sector has a well-known influence across all other industries (Ball and Grubnic, 2007), mainly through the design of regulations and policies as well as establishing a broad direction for how organisations will implement circular economy principles, thus serving as a good practice model (Domingues et al., 2018;

Ranängen et al., 2018). Adaptation to CE is thus a means of survival for companies, including public authorities, if they want to meet society's demand for long-term sustainable practices (Birgovan et al., 2022).

According to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (EMF), city governments play an important role in creating thriving, viable, and resilient cities that are regenerative by design. This key role is due to their proximity to the everyday concerns and needs of urban citizens and businesses, as well as the policy levers at their disposal. City governments frequently witness, experience, and manage the negative consequences of today's take-make-dispose linear economy, whether through public funds spent on solid waste management, structural waste costs such as the cost of underutilized buildings, economic costs due to congestion, or health costs due to air and noise pollution. Cities can help to catalyze broader system transformation. City governments have become more daring in driving such change in recent years (EMF, 2019).

City governments can engage, incentivize, manage, and establish a regulatory framework to create the conditions for the emergence of 21st-century cities. Cities can bring about changes in the use and management of materials within them by incorporating circular economy principles into urban policy levers; and urban priorities such as access to housing, mobility, and economic development can also be met in a way that supports prosperity, jobs, health, and communities. Cities, for example, can obtain products made from secondary raw materials or designed to be repairable and reusable. In this way, they can generate demand for circular innovations while also serving as a model for businesses and citizens to emulate.

Public procurement is the process by which the public - sector obtains works, goods, and services from businesses through the use of a public contract (Lozano and Witjes, 2016; 'Public Procurement - Growth - European Commission, n.d.). Construction, education, administration, transportation, office furniture, and other equipment are all included (Lozano and Witjes, 2016). Measuring cities' progress towards a circular economy also allows them to self-assess their achievements, identify barriers and opportunities, and adjust their development trajectory towards circularity as needed.

Thus, it is extremely important that we have a framework as realistic as possible to help the transition of cities to a circular economy. At the moment, there is no shared understanding of circular economy indicators in the literature or for the authorities that have decision-making power (Birgovan et al., 2022).

Traditional public procurement does not consider externalized environmental impact in its procurement process, instead focusing on product and service quality and the most cost-effective option. Given the large amount of money spent by government, public procurement has the market power to encourage the market penetration of circular products and services (Rizos, Behrens, Drabik, Rinaldi, and Tuokko, 2018). It can accomplish this by creating markets driven by public demand and promoting more sustainable business models by supporting national strategies, laws, and regulations that guide the procurement process at both the EU and national levels. Increased growth circular demand criteria at the national level. GPPs, for example, can promote resource-efficient products by advocating for increased product life, product design for ease of repair, refurbishment, disassembly, and recycling (Alhola et al., 2018).

The European Commission defined green public procurement (Green Public Procurement or GPP) in the Communication "Public procurement for an improved environment" as follows:

... "a process by which public authorities seek to purchase goods, services, and works that have a lower environmental impact throughout their life cycle when compared to other goods, services, and works that serve the same primary function."

2020 was an exceptional year, not only because of COVID-19, but also from the perspectives of research and policy relevant to Green Public Procurement. The EU Green Deal, which states that public authorities, including EU institutions, should lead by example and ensure that their purchases are green, has opened the door to new rules for Green Public Procurement over the last year. To ensure such progress, the Commission will propose new green public procurement legislation and guidelines (COM, 2020).

Modern consumption and growth patterns, characterized by high natural resource exploitation, rising emissions, and an extremely volatile economy, have led society down an extremely unsustainable path.

Indeed, resource depletion, increased pollution, and the rapid loss of biodiversity caused by the linear economic model have put the entire Earth system in jeopardy.

With these considerations in mind, we stopped for a moment at the city level to better comprehend the current situation in Romania regarding circular economy implementation and what is going on at the level of public institutions.

A study conducted in 2021 examined green public procurement in Romania, and the findings revealed that in our country, green procurement is not done frequently, and these factors are often overlooked (Bilan, 2021). The problem we address in the research is that there is no action at the level of public authorities in favor of the transition to a circular economy, and no green public procurement occurs, as required by the legal framework. As a result, the purpose of this study is to assist researchers in understanding why this is happening.

The current economic crisis is being blamed on the COVID-19 outbreak, which is the result of a breakdown in the global supply chain. In this regard, the pandemic has revealed the worst flaws of businesses and consumers, as well as their vulnerability to risk situations. Despite this, it has become clear that environmental sustainability is the way to face a situation of risk and uncertainty, which the supply chain faces; however, the economy faces an economic system of linear production, which presents a real challenge to achieve environmental sustainability, because resources are not used efficiently, and too much waste is generated. The public sector has a significant impact on today's and future societies. The public sector was chosen due to its critical role in societal change, and the way the circular economy is perceived and described in this field will have an influence on its smooth integration.

Methodology

The research design is cross-sectional and the data for all variables in the study were collected at the same time interval. A total of 122 questionnaires from representatives of public authorities from all Romania were collected via E-survey platform. Therefore, each individual received a link to participate in this study. They have been told that they need to report to the institution they belong to when completing the scale.

The participants included in this study were 35,25% males and 64.75% females. The average age of the sample was 44,8, more than half of the sample has a master degree and they are from 26 counties in Romania. Furthermore, 51.64 percent are from rural areas, while 48.36 percent are from urban areas. Less than 20% are unfamiliar with the concept of circular economy, while more than 70% are more familiar with the concept of sustainability.

In addition to descriptive analysis we ran a simple linear regression to see if public authorities' knowledge of the circular economy explains their CE and green public procurement behaviors, and if familiarity with the national green public procurement framework influences circular economy implementation.

Results

We discovered several intriguing aspects of Romanian public administration and have some good starting points for future research. According to the findings of this study, in the descriptive analysis it turned out that half of our sample, more specifically 50.82% declared that they know and understand what the circular economy is. We also wanted to identify which behaviors take place in order to be able to explore in the future if there are specific reasons why a series of behaviors take place more often and others not at all. The most common behaviors observed within the institutions included in this study are: selective waste collection, waste valorization, urban regeneration practices, and support for local producers.

We discovered that less than 20% of the institutions mentioned the circular economy concept in their strategic documents, an aspect that should not be overlooked and deserves to be explored further in the future.

Another intriguing finding in this study was that only 17.36% declared that they had submitted circular economy projects.

We wanted to see what the most common barriers are that prevent authorities from implementing EC in order to understand it more concretely. According to the findings of this study, the most common

perceived barriers by public officials are: a lack of people with expertise in the field, a lack of knowledge about the circular economy, a lack of funds allocated to this aspect, high prices, and a lack of information.

According to the descriptive analyses, very few green public procurements are made, and less than 10% claim to be familiar with the national framework of green public policies. IT equipment, energy efficiency, thermal wrapping, and buildings are the most common GPPs that occur within institutions.

Only 17.36 percent of those polled said they had received training in green public procurement, while 7.44 percent said they had received training in circular procurement.

We divided the sample into three groups based on their work experience for the inferential analyses (entry level, mid level and senior). We wanted to see if the implementation of the circular economy in institutions is related to their circular economy knowledge and seniority.

Following a simple regression, we discovered that this relationship is confirmed, and those with more than 7 years of work experience and familiarity with the concept of circular economy stated that more circular economy activities take place within their institution. At $p < 0.05$, this relationship is statistically significant.

Conclusions

According to the study's findings, very few institutions practise circular economy behaviours, which may be related to the fact that only a small percentage stated that they are very familiar with the national legislative framework for green procurement. This is an expectation that should be considered in future studies and explored during interviews.

We've shown why green procurement isn't common and what we can do to aid the transition to a green economy. Very few circular economy behaviours are carried out within institutions, which may be explained by the fact that only a small percentage stated that they are very familiar with the national legislative framework regarding green purchases. To intervene at any level, we must first understand at what level and how we should act. This article offers several suggestions to help with the transition.

The findings of this study serve as a foundation for future research on public authorities and the transition to a circular economy. We discovered some interesting aspects using the measurement tools, such as perceived barriers, the fact that these concepts do not appear in strategic documents, and there is no training, but we also investigated what kind of enablers could be very important in the transition.

Limits

The current study has some limitations, which should be considered when interpreting the study results. One limitation is that the sample size is insufficient to extrapolate to develop general assumptions on a larger scale.

Another constraint is the scale and the items we included. We recommend using interviews in future studies to ensure that we included the most important elements.

The cross-sectional correlation design requires only one measurement. As a result, explanations for the variables' dynamic nature cannot be generated, nor can causality be inferred. Another limitation of this design is that the data was collected using an online questionnaire, which meant that we had no control over environmental conditions that could interfere with the accuracy of the answers, altering those who followed the results. Also, keep in mind that people can provide desirable responses.

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